

Role of Visual Training Instructor in Enhancement of Sports Performance

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ARTICLE DETAILS

Research Paper

Keywords:

visual training, sports performance, visual training instructor.

DOI;

10.5281/zenodo.14294638

ABSTRACT

Sports coaches, athletes, and sports scientists are constantly pursuing modern training methods to improve sports performance and gain a competitive advantage. Visual training is extremely important for the coach to understand the function of vision during sports performance and skill practice. Sports vision helps the sportsman determine how well their eyes perform and what should be done to improve their performance. Sports visual training is a personalized form of vision therapy aimed at developing specific visual skills in athletes. Four research reviews justifying the need for visual training instructors are analyzed systematically in this study. On the basis of the literature review, it can be understood that visual training has numerous benefits for athletes in almost all sports and games. The qualities of a visual training instructor, the tools used in vision training, and the need for a visual training instructor are discussed in this article.

Introduction

Numerous research is currently being conducted in an effort to identify the most complete training regimen for athletes. Similar to this, sports coaches, players, and sports scientists are always

looking for cutting-edge training techniques to boost athletic performance and acquire a competitive edge. For the coach to fully comprehend how vision functions during athletic performance and skill practice, visual training is crucial. Sports training programs frequently focus on visual and visual motor skills due to the perceived demanding nature of sports. Programs for vision training have been around for a while. However, there has been a significant increase in new digital technologies over the past few years, which will alter the sport vision training program and lower the risk of sports-related injuries. The significance of vision training is evident from the way it has influenced how people perceive their daily experiences and, particularly, how it has improved sports performance. Similar to this, current research emphasizes the value of visual abilities in athletic performance. With low vision, the majority of athletic activities are performed poorly. Many physical education teachers and coaches may not be aware of information regarding human vision that is pertinent to sport, despite the fact that they are aware of safety precautions and protective gear for the eyes in many sports. Any sport places high demands on the visual system, and visual training can have an impact on how well an athlete can do the necessary tasks for their sport. Numerous studies have demonstrated the superiority of a visual training program.

Concept of visual training

Sports vision enables athletes to assess the performance of their eyes and what has to be done to enhance that performance. Sports visual training is a specialized form of vision treatment designed to help athletes improve their specific visual abilities. Athletes that participate in this form of training will see an improvement in their visual skills in their chosen sport.

Research reviews justifying the need for visual training instructor

The instructor or director of vision training is the one who prepare and train the prerequisite to enhance the visual ability of the individual participating in any activity or sport. There have already been several surveys on visual training in sport and these surveys have described the results of vision training in sports training as follows.

Flad & Shalady (2019) conducted an empirical study titled- Effects of visual exercise on service performance for junior volleyball female players. The results showed that visual exercises are effective in improving service skills for junior female volleyball players. Their study showed that the visual exercise or training program improved the visual ability of the experimental group compared with the control group. Visual exercise or training with the control group improved the technical performance of

the experimental group's serve skills. Also, visual exercise or training has proven to be effective in improving visual ability and volleyball serve skills.

Appelbaum et. al., (2016) examined the effects of sports vision training on collegiate softball athletes examined the impact of sports vision training on sensory abilities through data collected during training conducted by the University of Texas University's varsity softball team. In one survey, a sports visual training program showed improvement in sensory skills.

Du Toit et. al, (2007) studied the effects of exercise on the performance of female rugby players. Visual training or performance was required for female as well as male Rugby players to achieve maximum results or performance on the field of play. The results suggest that with the right training programs and proper hand-eye coordination tests, widespread improvement in sports performance can be achieved. The survey also aimed to improve visual coordination, attention and motor processes over rival athletes.

According to Sowden & Cardinale (2018) investigated the effectiveness of different visual skills training programs on elite cricket players. The study examined the impact of sports vision training on male cricketer's visual skills and batting performance. The result revealed that sports vision training showed a significant improvement on visual skills and batting performance of male cricketers. According to this study, sports vision training is an effective way to improve the visual skills and batting performance of cricketers.

On the basis of the literature review, it can be understood that visual training has numerous benefits for athletes in almost all sports and games. Following are enumerated some of the benefits:

- It improves dynamic visual accuracy.
- It improves peripheral vision.
- It improves depth perception.
- It improves eye--hand-body coordination.
- It developed visualization.
- It improves visual concentration.
- It improves the visual reaction time.
- It developed movement quickly.

- And overall performance enhanced.

Some of the tools that can be used to prevent traumatic events during vision training are Contact lenses, Sports eyewear, sunglass lenses, Tinted glasses, and Swimming glasses.

Qualities of visual training instructor

1. Knowing the anatomy of eye.
2. Planning the vision training session.
3. Training to use tools related to modern vision training.
4. Having the knowledge to look at training from simplicity to complexity.
5. Ensuring continuity in training.
6. Must have knowledge of the training duration and training load.
7. Motivating the participants and guiding them in right direction.

Need for a visual training instructor

A visual trainer can considerably enhance the sports performance of athletes in almost all sports and games. A visual training instructor equipped with appropriate knowledge should be considered an asset to any sporting team. The physiological and psychological makeup of sportspeople will be taken care of by the coaches. The peripheral vision, visual acuity, visual perception, and accuracy of sight of sportspersons should be taken care of for better performance. A number of studies support this notion. The appointment of a visual training instructor may drastically enhance sports performance. It may help Indian sportspersons perform on par with foreign sportspersons. He can employ various measures to improve his visual capacity, especially peripheral vision and dynamic acuity. Further, measures to keenly observe the equipment (e.g., the ball) amidst various distractions may be included in the visual training program.

Conclusion

A closer look at all of these points reveals the importance of visual training. All four of the aforementioned vision training research surveys have been conducted overseas. None of the research

was found to have been conducted in India. By adopting the results of this type of study, it will be possible to visually train the sportspersons in Indian conditions. It is possible to make significant progress in all sports by employing a visual training instructor in every university, college, coaching centre, sports federation, Sports Authority of India, and so on.

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